

**THE CONTRIBUTION OF HOJI MUIN, SON OF SHUKRULLO, TO THE
NATIONAL PRESS AND EDUCATION OF TURKESTAN**

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Turkiston jadidchilik harakatining ma'rifatparvar namoyondalaridan biri Hoji Muin Shukrullo o'g'lining milliy matbuotimiz, adabiyot, maktab va maorif tizimi rivoji uchun qilgan sa'y-harakatlari, badiiy asarlari hamda publitsistik maqolalaridagi ta'limiy-axloqiy qarashlari haqida fikr yuritilgan.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются усилия Хаджи Муина Шукрулло, одного из просвещенных представителей Туркестанского революционного движения, по развитию нашей национальной печати, литературы, школьной и образовательной системы, его художественные произведения, его воспитательно-нравственные взгляды в публицистических статьях.*

Abstract: *This article discusses the efforts of Haji Muin Shukrullo o'g'li, one of the enlightened representatives of the Turkestan Jadid movement, for the development of our national press, literature, schools, and education system, as well as the educational and moral views expressed in his artistic works and journalistic articles.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Usuli jadid, Guldastayi adabiyot, milliy matbuot, tatbiqoti diniya, maktabdor, usuli qadim, Muxtasari jug'rofiyayi umumiy;*

The late 19th and early 20th centuries in Turkestan are considered a period of profound socio-political and educational transformation.

The main reason for this shift was the emergence of the Jadidism movement, which first appeared in the 1880s in the Caucasus.

The word "Jadid" originates from Arabic and means "new."

Among the leaders of the Jadidism movement in Turkestan were Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Saidahmad Siddiqiy, Abdulla Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, Is'hoqkhon Ibrat, Abduqodir Shakuri, and Muhammadsharif Sofizoda.

Alongside these prominent figures, Hoji Muin, son of Shukrullo, also held a significant place as a dedicated follower of Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, who was considered a leading figure of the progressive intellectuals of Turkestan.

Hoji Muin was a prominent enlightener and reformer who fought for the progress and development of the nation. Hoji Muin was born on March 19, 1883, in Samarkand. Having lost his parents at an early age, the young Muin was raised by his grandfather. During this time, he managed to learn basic reading and writing, and later went on to study Arabic grammar and religious sciences in depth.

His acquaintance with Sayidahmad Vasliy, a well-known intellectual of that period, created a favorable environment for Hoji Muin's future activities. In addition to teaching him the rules of Arabic grammar, Vasliy also introduced him to the world of poetry.

Hoji Muin initially worked as a teacher in a traditional school. Under the influence of Abduqodir Shakuri's new method school, he opened his own school in 1903.

For the first time, he met Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, known as the father of Turkestan Jadidism, at the home of his teacher S. Vasliy.

This meeting marked the beginning of a new chapter in Hoji Muin's life. In particular, Behbudi's book titled "Mukhtasari Jug'rofiyayi Umumiy" (A Brief General Geography) made a profound impression on him.

Later, in one of his articles, Hoji Muin recalled:

"I can never forget that in the chapter 'Religious Applications' of this geography book, I read the following sentence:

'Some of the old superstitions and Isra'iliyyat (Judaic legends) have even made their way into our books of tafsir (Qur'anic commentary).' Those words brought a powerful change in my thinking at that time. That sentence caused me to experience my first intellectual revolution. From that moment on, I became a true admirer of Behbudi Efendi, and since then, I have always defended him whenever the opportunity arose." [1, pp. 5–6b]

At that time, the national press reflected noble ideas such as saving the people from the quagmire of ignorance and educating them, which were widely promoted by Jadid publicists through their articles.

Hoji Muin, too, understood the crucial role of the press in realizing these high aspirations. Taking up the pen, he began his journalistic activity.

In the July 9, 1918 issue of the newspaper "The Voice of the Workers", an article by Hoji Muin titled "Family Upbringing" was published.

In this article, he discusses the importance of the family in society, how essential it is for the development of every individual, and how a well-educated and morally grounded generation is key to the prosperity of the nation.

He describes the family as a fortress that raises such a generation and writes:

“For every nation in the world to live with rights and happiness, it must be capable of adopting the knowledge and culture of its time. Likewise, for a family to live a happy and comfortable life, its members must be properly brought up and educated.

There is no nation in the world that has progressed without proper family upbringing. And there is no family whose members, without being educated, can live a truly happy and prosperous life.”

Hoji Muin condemned ignorance as one of the main obstacles to the progress of society.

He repeatedly emphasized that many nations have vanished from the pages of history precisely due to a lack of knowledge.

In his article, he stresses not only the importance of educating boys within the family, but also insists on the literacy and education of girls and women:

“We, the people of Turkestan, have been striving for about fifteen years to progress and flourish like others in the world by opening new schools.

We have started educating only our sons, but until now, we have paid no attention to the education of our daughters.

Yet we still hope that in the future, prosperous families will emerge from among us, and that we too will become advanced and civilized like others.

However, we must realize and believe, from this very moment, that until we educate both our sons and daughters together, our society will never produce truly happy and prosperous families. And we will never attain the ideals of true happiness, progress, and civilization that we dream of.”

Between 1907 and 1937, Hoji Muin actively contributed to the intellectual sphere through over 200 articles, nearly 400 news pieces, and approximately 1,500 poetic lines written in Uzbek and Tajik, published in 23 different newspapers and journals, as recorded in his personal diaries [3].

Among his enduring literary legacy are biographical writings, articles on contemporary socio-political issues, satirical essays, and dramatic works such as “Old School, New School”,

“Mazluma Khotun”, and “Ko‘knori” (The Poppy).

Hoji Muin was also active and productive as a translator.

From Turkish, he translated “Khulāsai Qavā’idi Forsi” (A Summary of Persian Grammar), and from Persian, he translated “The Journey to Bukhara”, a work attributed to Abdurauf Fitrat, into Uzbek.

His short story “The Uninvited Guest” is considered among his unpublished works, and some of his writings have unfortunately been lost over time.

In 1915, Hoji Muin compiled a collection titled “New Literature” (Yangi Adabiyot) for third-grade students of primary schools, which included poems by contemporary poets of Turkestan.

In his dramatic works such as “Mazluma Khotun”, “Ko‘knori” (The Poppy), and “Toy” (The Wedding), he criticized harmful customs and outdated traditions that were prevalent among the people at that time [1, p. 8b].

In the November 24, 1911 edition of the newspaper “Turkiston Viloyatining Gazeti” (The Province of Turkestan Newspaper),

Hoji Muin published an article titled “The Benefits of Reading Newspapers.” In it, he wrote:

“Reading newspapers is not yet a common custom or practice among us, the people of Turkestan.

If we truly understood the benefits of reading newspapers, or even grasped their meaning, we would never give up reading them, not even for a moment.

...Most of our people do not read newspapers at all.

And among those who do, nine out of ten cannot benefit from them properly, because they lack even the basic knowledge of history and geography.” [1, p. 56b]

With these words, he revealed the deep-rooted backwardness in society and called upon the public to take up the habit of reading newspapers.

During his career, Hoji Muin founded a satirical newspaper called “Tayoq” (The Stick).

Regarding the title, he explained that despite long-standing efforts to educate the nation and bring about progress similar to other peoples, his attempts were obstructed by widespread laziness and arrogance among the population—vices that hindered progress and enlightenment.

Hoji Muin was also productive as a translator.

He translated: (A Summary of Persian Grammar) from Turkish, and “Journey to Bukhara”, a work written by Fitrat, from Persian into Uzbek.

His story titled “The Uninvited Guest” is among his unpublished works, and some of his other writings have been lost. In 1915, Hoji Muin compiled an anthology called “New Literature” (Yangi Adabiyot) for third-grade students in primary schools, featuring poems by contemporary poets of Turkestan. In his plays “Mazluma Khotun”, “Ko‘knori” (The Poppy), and “The Wedding” (To‘y), he criticized harmful customs and social vices that had become widespread among the population [1, p. 8b]. In the November 24, 1911 issue of “Turkiston Viloyatining Gazeti” (The Turkestan Regional Newspaper), Hoji Muin published an article titled “The Benefit of Reading Newspapers”, in which he wrote:

“For us, the people of Turkestan, reading newspapers is not yet a common habit or tradition.

If we truly understood the benefit of reading, or if we grasped its meaning, we would never give up newspaper reading, not even for a moment.

...Most of our people do not read newspapers at all.

And among those who do, nine out of ten fail to benefit from them properly, because they have little to no knowledge of history and geography.” [1, p. 56b]

Through such words, he exposed the deep-rooted ignorance in society and urged people to engage in reading and critical thought.

Throughout his career, Hoji Muin also founded a satirical newspaper called “Tayoq” (meaning The Stick).

Explaining the reason for this name, he wrote that despite his long-standing efforts to promote literacy and development, his goals were often blocked by the laziness and arrogance he observed in society—flaws which, in his view, severely hindered national progress.

"A Scene from a New School.

The school building complies with hygiene regulations; maps are attached to the walls.

On one side, the teacher sits at a desk. In front of him is a table ("miz"), and beside him is a board.

Across from him, four students sit at two desks. On another side, three or four chairs are arranged...” [1, p. 201b]

The activities of the Jadid schools were regularly opposed by supporters of traditional (old method) schools.

Nevertheless, the Jadids did not position their “usuli jadid” (new method) schools as being in direct conflict with the traditional “usuli qadim” (old method) schools.

On this matter, Ismail Gaspirali wrote:

“Let not what we write here offend the teachers of old-method schools, our respected brothers.

After all, we ourselves studied through the old method...

Reforming the national schools handed down from our forefathers is what we mean by the new method — it does not mean creating a completely new education or a completely different school.” [2, p. 146b]

The main difference between Jadid schools and old-method schools was that Jadid schools enabled the people to become literate in a short period of time, and they demonstrated practical ways of teaching and learning.

Like other enlightened Jadids of his time, Hoji Muin also established his own school. In order to educate children, he did not collect funds from the public; instead, he grew fruit through gardening, sold it in the market, and used the money to support his educational efforts.

He never sought any material gain from being a school owner or educator.

Hoji Muin also translated a number of Turkic poems with educational value into Persian for children.

With the support of Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, he compiled and published them as a collection titled “Guldastayi Adabiyot” (A Literary Bouquet).

In addition to the translated poems, the collection also included original works by Hoji Muin himself, such as: Nasihat (Advice), Kitob va Gūdaki Beilm (An Address and the Ignorant Child), Ittifoq (Unity), Muxammas (A traditional five-line stanza), E’tirof (Confession), Shikoyat (Complaint)

In conclusion, Hoji Muin, son of Shukrullo, remains a progressive and devoted Uzbek intellectual who dedicated his entire life to the cause of national independence, public enlightenment, free thought, and the advancement of his nation. Studying Hoji Muin’s articles, poems, plays, and satires helps us to better understand the national press, literature, and the rich legacy of our Jadid forefathers from that era.

Hoji Muin, son of Shukrullo (1883–1942)

LIST OF REFERENCES USED:

- Compiled and prepared for publication by: B. Dustqorayev, N. Namozova; *Selected Works // Hoji Muin; Expanded 2nd edition – Tashkent: Ma’naviyat, 2010* O. Hasanboyev, J. Hasanboyev,
J. Hamidov, “*History of Pedagogy*”, Tashkent: O‘qituvchi Publishing House, 1997
<https://kh-davron.uz/kutubxona/jadidlar-kutubxona/begali-qosimov-hoji-muin-qismati.html>
<https://n.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/uzbek-sheriyati/o-zbek-mumtoz-adabiyoti/hoji-muin-1883-1942>